

A Study of the Nature of Slope (S_v) of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} Curves for some Tetra-alkylammonium Salts in Formamide-DMSO Solvent Mixture at 25°. Part-III

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Four salts Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI have been examined in formamide DMSO (non-aqueous solvents mixtures) from the point of view of apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) study by the magnetic float densitometer method. Two concentration ranges (0.002–0.012M and 0.02–0.12M) of solutions have been selected. The trend in ϕ_v and hence the nature of the slope of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves has been studied for these salts. Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI show transition in the sign of slope in dilute solutions, but they show positive slope in concentrated solutions. Et_4NI has positive nature in its slope in lower as well as in higher concentrations.

The dependence of the slope of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves on the dielectric constant of the solvent medium has been examined earlier¹ by studying the behaviour of the slope for some tetra-alkyl ammonium salts in *N*-methylacetamide (NMA)+ dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) mixtures. This type of mixture provided us the solvent media of various dielectric constants. Out of the two components of the solvents selected, one was chosen as having very high dielectric constant (NMA) and the other, a very low dielectric constant (DMSO). One point needs to be emphasised here in selecting the solvents is that both the solvents are nonaqueous ones. To extend our study further, a similar solvent mixture, viz. formamide + DMSO has been selected here.

The idea of selecting formamide and DMSO pair came from the fact that the previous studies of tetraalkyl salts in dimethyl sulphoxide² revealed that the slope of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curve was always positive in the concentration range studied. The sign of the slope of higher tetraalkyl salts (Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI , Pen_4NI) became negative when these were tested in formamide by some workers³. Also to see the validity of Frank's hypothesis on enforced water structure⁴ to solvents other than water.

Results and Discussion

Apparent molal volume data are given in Table 1. From the concentration and apparent molal volume data, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI were drawn for both concentration ranges and using four compositions of the formamide and DMSO. Only one such representative graph (Fig. 1) is given here. S_v values and the corresponding ϵ values for different solvent mixtures for all the salts are given in Table 2.

It is to be pointed out that the dielectric constant values of formamide + DMSO mixtures of varying compositions have not appeared in the

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAL VOLUME OF TETRAETHYL AMMONIUM IODIDE
0% Formamide in DMSO ($d_0 = 1.101$ 232 g ml⁻¹)

Sl. no.	<i>m</i>	<i>w</i> g	<i>i</i> mA	<i>d</i> g ml ⁻¹	\sqrt{c}	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Low concentration :						
1.	0.002	8.950	176	1.101 399	0.047	164.25
2.	0.004	9.000	156	1.101 566	0.066	164.65
3.	0.006	9.050	135	1.101 730	0.081	164.80
4.	0.008	9.100	115	1.101 895	0.094	165.05
5.	0.010	9.150	95	1.102 060	0.105	165.10
6.	0.012	9.200	75	1.102 220	0.115	165.40
High concentration :						
1.	0.02	9.300	45	1.102 788	0.148	169.10
2.	0.04	9.350	87	1.104 297	0.209	169.85
3.	0.06	9.600	17	1.105 788	0.255	170.50
4.	0.08	9.700	20	1.107 230	0.294	170.25
5.	0.10	9.800	37	1.108 640	0.328	171.30
6.	0.12	9.900	49	1.110 090	0.358	171.55

literature so far. These values have been found out by assuming a linear relationship between composition of the solvent mixture and its dielectric constant (Table 3).

Et_4NI gives positive S_v values in all the four compositions of formamide and DMSO over the entire concentration range selected. Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI salts indicate the change of sign of slope (from positive to negative) as the dielectric constant of the medium is increased by increasing the formamide content in the mixture if the solutions are very dilute. But in case of concentrated solutions there is no change in the positive nature

TABLE 2— S_V VALUES FOR SOME R_4NI -SALTS IN FORMAMIDE+DMSO MIXTURES AT 25°

Formamide (% v/v) in DMSO	Dielectric constants as manipulated by graph ϵ	S_V value ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mole}^{-1/2} \text{litre}^{1/2} \text{dm}^{-3/2}$)							
		Et_4NI		Pr_4NI		Bu_4NI		Pen_4NI	
		Low concn.	High concn.	Low concn.	High concn.	Low concn.	High concn.	Low concn.	High concn.
0	46.6	17.10	11.90	5.88	1.82	6.25	1.45	13.51	3.45
20	59.0	10.00	3.33	10.80	9.10	4.08	3.57	-4.65	2.38
40	71.6	7.2	2.6	-8.00	7.00	-2.5	2.44	-10.00	1.32
60	84.0	5.26	1.74	-15.22	5.00	-8.8	1.11	-21.60	0.96

 Fig. 1. Plots of ϕ_V vs \sqrt{c} for Et_4NI in formamide+DMSO mixtures at 25°; concentration range, 0.002–0.012M.

of the slope for these salts. There are three interesting features in the present investigation. Firstly, Et_4NI has a positive slope in lower as well as in higher concentrations. Secondly, for remaining three salts Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI , the lower range of concentrations indicates a transition in the sign of slope from positive to negative, on increasing dielectric constants of the mixture while the higher range of concentration does not show such transition. Thirdly, Pr_4NI and Bu_4NI show the

TABLE 3—DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF FORMAMIDE + DMSO MIXTURES AT 25°

Sl. no.	Formamide (% v/v) in DMSO	ϵ
1.	0	46.6
2.	20	59.0
3.	40	71.6
4.	60	84.0
5.	80	96.6
6.	100	109.5

transition in the sign of S_V from positive to negative at a lower dielectric constant medium (between 0% ($\epsilon=46.6$) and 20% ($\epsilon=59.0$) formamide) whereas the Pen_4NI gives this transition at a little higher dielectric constant medium (between 20% ($\epsilon=59.0$) and 40% ($\epsilon=71.6$) formamide). The picture is more clear when the S_V values are plotted against the dielectric constants (ϵ) of the medium (Figs. 2 and 3). Fig. 2 shows the points of inflexion for Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in dilute solutions more clearly and explicitly. The positive sign of slope changes over to negative at $\epsilon=57.5$ for Pr_4NI , at $\epsilon=67$ for Bu_4NI and at $\epsilon=61$ for Pen_4NI . There is no such change in case of Et_4NI . Fig. 3 does not show the change in the sign of the slope from positive to negative upto the range of dielectric constant medium selected in the present study (60% formamide ($\epsilon=84.0$)). The only thing which is common in both these graphs is that the curve becomes more and more steeper as we go from Et_4NI to Pen_4NI .

 Fig. 2. Plots of S_V vs ϵ for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in formamide+DMSO mixtures at 25°; concentration range 0.002–0.012M.

Fig. 3. Plots of S_v vs ϵ for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in formamide+DMSO mixtures at 25° ; concentration range 0.02–0.12M.

The increase of ϕ_v with the increase in salt concentration and the dependence of sign of slope on dielectric constant of the medium and the nature of the electrolyte ion are explained below. There are mainly three factors which influence the ionic interactions in solutions at a given temperature, namely, the concentration of the salt, the nature and size of electrolyte ion, and the dielectric constant of the medium. Generally the increase of ϕ_v with the increase of salt concentration (that is a positive slope) is due to increase in the volume of solution on adding the salt (additive property). But it is not always true, particularly when the bigger molecules, like higher tetra-alkyl salts, are taken. The ionic interaction is very much affected due to interpenetration of ions (of solvent or electrolyte). The smaller ion penetrates into the void spaces formed by the cage of bigger ion and the addition of salt does not contribute towards the increase in volume. This results in the decrease of ϕ_v on increasing salt concentration (that is a negative slope). This explanation is valid upto a certain limit of concentration (lower concentration range) but beyond this concentration limit (higher concentration range) the additive property dominates over the interpenetration effect and again ϕ_v starts increasing with salt concentration.

For very dilute solutions, the number of bigger ions is very small and the interpenetration of ions in such solutions is unable to start but no sooner the number of such ions increases a little more, the interpenetration effect sets in, causing a negative slope.

Furthermore, the ionic interactions depend very much on the dielectric constant of the medium (interaction forces are inversely proportional to the dielectric constant of the medium). In the medium of low dielectric constant the ionic interactions are strong, but as the dielectric constant of the medium is increased interactions become weak. The high ionic interactions favour positive slope while the weak interactions lead to negative slope. Our results clearly indicate the dependence of dielectric constant on the S_v values giving the transition points in certain cases. So the behaviour of the electrolytes in this particular non-aqueous mixture is the resultant of all the three effects discussed here.

Experimental

Formamide³ (E. Merck) was recrystallised and distilled under reduced pressure, the middle fraction being redistilled under reduced pressure. Samples of the formamide having electrical conductance of the order of 10^{-8} mho or less, were used in the present investigation. The DMSO solvent was purified in the manner as described earlier¹. The R_4N -iodides (tetra-alkylammonium iodides) were purified as described in the literature⁵. Mixtures of formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide of different compositions (0, 20, 40 and 60% (v/v) formamide) were prepared. Density of the solvent mixtures was measured at 25° by the magnetic float densitometer⁶.

Then the solutions of Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI were prepared on molal basis using the solvent mixtures of different composition. Two ranges of the electrolyte concentrations, lower (0.002–0.012M) and higher (0.02–0.12M), were selected as earlier¹. The weight (w) and the corresponding value of the hold-down current (i) were measured for each solution and then the density was calculated⁶, and from which the apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) was calculated for each concentration by the usual formula. The observations are given in Table I for pure DMSO⁷.

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